

WWRF #52,
Plenary Session 2: Hexa-X-II Workshop
London, 10 September 2024

Key results on Radio Evolution & Innovation

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Hexa-X-II

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Key results on Sustainability and Acceptability

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Main environmental, social and economic challenges

Maximizing the adoption of renewable energy sources and the integration of smart grid technologies depending on the country and the respective regulations

Comprehensive lifecycle assessments are pivotal to understand the hotspots in a product or system, but simpler and applicable methodologies are needed to be used more broadly.

Social engagement and building trust in the use of the new technologies while taking into account cultural and regulatory aspects of all countries.

Increasing network investments due to e.g., increased amount of data, and infrastructure costs for digital inclusion.

Building new business models, e.g., new types of collaborations, contracts and financial flows, and incentives for attracting large investments for the benefit of the society.

Objectives

Methodology

Surveys on advanced communication services - Main outcomes

- Numerous government and private institutions engage in conducting opinion surveys to understand the public perception of the evolving digital environments.
- Dynamic nature of social acceptability concerning technological advancements, influenced by diverse factors such as COVID-19, cultural norms, individual beliefs, ethical considerations, and perceived societal impact.
- Technology adoption and usage behavior are chiefly shaped by environmental awareness, curiosity, facilitating conditions, and perceived satisfaction, highlighting the multifaceted nature of user preferences.
- Potential effectiveness of public environmental awareness campaigns in dispelling misconceptions, emphasizing the eco-friendly nature of advanced telecommunication technologies, and its minimal impact on privacy and the ecological system.
- HEXA X II is planning a workshop on the 30th of October with 6G4Society on acceptability of 6G.

Sustainability Guidelines for 6G Design

Environmental Sustainability

Environmental Sustainability

- **Environmental sustainability** as key consideration in the planning, architecture, and operation of 6G networks
- **Holistic Approach to Different Footprints and Trade-offs:**
 - Consider different footprints (carbon, water, resources, land, biodiversity, etc.) and trade-offs between sustainability factors
 - Adopt a fully comprehensive life cycle assessment (LCA) approach to 6G equipment and devices
- **Alternative Materials:**
 - Avoid hazardous substances in 6G infrastructure components
- **Design 6G equipment to be modular and durable:**
 - Extend hardware lifespan, customize easily, scale efficiently, speed up repair and maintenance processes leading to increased system availability and reduced downtime
 - Reduce waste generation by enabling reusability and recycling

Environmental Sustainability

- **Energy Efficiency:**
 - Minimize energy consumption in production and operation phases
 - Use low-power components, optimize network architecture and protocols, implement energy-efficient algorithms and management systems
 - Optimize equipment and processes, reduce fluorinated gases, conserve energy and water
- **Energy Sourcing:**
 - Incorporate renewable and fossil-free electricity
- **Cloud Computing and Automation:**
 - Reduce energy consumption linked to data transmission by implementing edge computing
 - Move processing power closer to end users/devices, particularly IoT devices, to minimize data transmission
 - Implement automated systems to manage network and device states according to demand
- **Circularity Practices:**
 - Adopt circularity practices in 6G network production and operation
 - Use renewable resources, such as bioplastics and green energy
 - Promote reusing, refurbishing, recycling, and repairing components
 - Design equipment for easy disassembly and responsible end-of-life disposal

Environmental Requirements and Considerations for 6G

➤ Governmental and Intergovernmental Work

- UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)
 - The goals should be reached by 2030, when 6G is expected to be available in the market.
- UN Framework Convention on Climate Change (FCCC)
 - Companies are supposed to reach net zero around 2040-2050, following a 1.5°C aligned emissions reduction pathway corresponding to halving emissions by 2030
 - Two main initiatives around net zero and emission reduction are the Science-Based Targets Initiative (SBTi) and the Race to Zero
- Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC)
 - 6th Assessment report: Pathways consistent with 1.5°C carbon budgets imply rapid, deep, and immediate GHG emission reductions in all sectors
- EU Green Deal, EU accessibility act, General Data Protection Regulation
- Body of European Regulators for Electronic Communications (BEREC)
 - Harmonized assessment methodology and transparency measures regarding the environmental footprint of electronic communications networks and services (ECN/ECS)
- Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services (ISPRES)
 - Stakeholders activities to support the achievement of the post-2020 global biodiversity framework and the 2050 Vision for Biodiversity

➤ End-users' growing concerns

Standardization Organizations and Industry Associations

- International Telecommunication Union (ITU)
 - Area of action for environment and climate change: definitions and recommendations for sustainable ICTs
 - Main activities: Monitoring, mitigation, and adaptation to climate change – reduce e-waste – digital solutions – greening ITU itself
- European Telecommunications Standards Institute (ETSI)
 - Environmental Engineering committee: networks and services, circular economy standards, etc.
 - Access, Terminals, Transmission and Multiplexing committee: energy efficiency/management KPIs, Eco-design of products
 - Industry Specification Group on Operational energy Efficiency for Users: Energy consumption of IT servers, broadband fixed access, mobile access, end-of-life of ICT, etc.
- Global system Mobile Association (GSMA)
 - Sustainability Assessment Framework, the Climate Hub, AgriTech, Ecosystem accelerator, etc.
 - A more resilient future
- Next Generation Mobile Networks Alliance (NGMN)
 - A series of whitepapers on “Green Future Networks”- KPIs and target values for green network assessment
 - Key considerations for 6G include enabling a seamless and affordable experience, focusing on sustainability and energy efficiency, taking a holistic approach to development, and considering user terminal and service design to optimize resource usage and reduce waste.
- Next G Alliance (NGA) – Green G working group
 - A working group within the NGA, focusing on promoting environmental sustainability in the development of future wireless technology
 - Sustainable 6G ecosystem and enabling other industries to reduce GHG emissions, limit land and water use, and move towards circular economy
 - Two whitepapers: “Green G: The Path Toward Sustainable 6G” and “6G Sustainability KPI Assessment: Introduction and Gap Analysis”

Environmental Frameworks for 6G

The Planetary Boundaries Framework

- A global initiative aimed at safeguarding Earth's critical life-supporting systems
- Key Elements
 - 1. Critical Earth Systems**

Nine fundamental planetary processes vital for Earth's stability, including climate and biodiversity
 - 2. Safe Operating Limits**

Scientifically-based thresholds for each process, indicating how much change is acceptable without triggering irreversible harm
 - 3. Environmental Tipping Points**

Importance of avoiding tipping points, where abrupt and potentially catastrophic shifts in Earth systems occur
- Several initiatives to translate these boundaries to actionable boundaries that could be applied by companies: The Earth Commission of Future Earth, the Global Commons Alliance and Science Based Targets Networks (SBTN) work to operationalise boundaries.

Power Consumption and Decarbonization of Energy Sources

- Increase in the number of connected devices and the amount of data transmitted per user
- High energy efficiency and renewable energy sources
- For communication service providers, most of the power consumption comes from the RAN (73% of the total energy consumption of the telecom network)
- Radio equipment accounts for 29% of total consumption

Energy Consumption Breakdown for a CSP

Nokia Bell Labs source

Power Consumption Breakdown for a mMIMO RU at Full Load

- Objective:
 - Make 6G socially sustainable and
 - 6G technologies to support social sustainability
- Social sustainability aspects for making 6G networks socially sustainable are Trustworthiness and Digital Inclusion.
- Main drivers have been identified:
 - 6G solutions and networks need to be cyber-secure and respect end-users privacy;
 - AI-based approaches need to be clear, transparent and keep the human in the loop / require interaction with human operators when critical decisions need to be taken so that accountability, and thus trust, can be maintained;
 - 6G networks need to be flexible and adjustable in terms of capacity and coverage depending on the areas and the end-users' characteristics, as well as the criticality of the offered solutions, e.g., e-health aspects vs. entertainment;
 - 6G solutions need to be non-discriminatory, e.g., take into account IT literacy and culture of all types of end-users; and
 - 6G network availability in terms of both coverage and capacity needs to be ensured at certain levels (depending on the services offered) to maintain people's trust in digital capabilities and services.

Next Steps

- Development of a value-centered approach to 6G: Env., social and economic values
- Beyond performance: Joint optimization of KVIs and KPIs
- Assessment of Hexa-X-II use cases for their enablement potential (ITU-T-L1480: first, second, higher order effects)
- Analysis of the challenges and risks to meet environmental sustainability requirements
- Validate 6G use cases that result in a net positive effect on the planet
- Exploring the rebound effects that could potentially offset the enablement potential of an ICT solution
- Trade-offs with other sustainability aspects: health, governance, institutional, cultural, ethical, etc.

- D1.1: “Environmental, societal and economical drivers and goals for 6G”, June 2023.
- D1.2: “6G use cases and requirements”, Dec. 2023.
- D1.3: “Environmental and societal impacts of 6G”, Mar. 2024
- *D1.4: “6G Value, requirements and ecosystem”, Apr. 2025.*

<https://hexa-x-ii.eu/results/>

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Key results on Radio Evolution & Innovation from WP4

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- From CoMP to D-MIMO Systems
- Recap of results from Hexa-X
- Overview of ongoing work in Hexa-X-II
- Take home messages

From CoMP to D-MIMO Systems

B4G

Source: ARTIST4G

6G(?)

5G/B5G

Source: mmMAGIC

With RIS/NCR(?)

CoMP: Coordinated Multi-Point

D-MIMO: Distributed Multiple-Input Multiple-Output

D-MIMO Radio Architecture Studies

Architectural options for D-MIMO

D-MIMO with wireless fronthaul operating at high bands while access links at low bands.

1. Transport media: The backhaul/fronthaul can either be wired or wireless.
2. Signalling: Digitally encoded or analogue signal modulated onto a carrier.
3. Processing: Can either be performed analogue/digital or centralized/distributed.
4. Transmission: Coherent or non-coherent

Distributed MIMO with key design options

Conclusions

- Densification key enabler to meet coverage and reliability targets at higher frequency bands – there seems to be sufficient spectrum available.
- Thus, low-cost solutions are more important than spectral efficiency, at least in the early roll-out phases.
- In the lower mmW bands the need for higher spectral efficiency calls for digital less distributed approaches.

MIMO Transmissions - D4.2

D4.2 - Radio Design and Spectrum Access requirements and key enablers for 6G Evolution • 31/10/2023

D-MIMO schemes and architectures

Coherent joint transmission

Non-coherent joint transmission

Decentralized Transmission

RIS-assisted integrated access and backhaul

KPIs: spectral efficiency, BER, cell capacity, throughput, coverage

KPIs: Energy consumption reduction, reduced cost

- Sustainability: reduced energy consumption
- Inclusiveness: coverage extension
- Trustworthiness: higher reliability

D-MIMO schemes and architectures

Multi-antenna coded-caching

Joint UE / AP selection for scalable transmission

EMF evaluation for distributed transmissions

Distributed massive MIMO for MTC

KPIs: spectral efficiency, Latency, BER, cell capacity, throughput, coverage

KPIs: Energy consumption reduction, reduced complexity

- Sustainability: reduced EMF exposure
- Inclusiveness: coverage extension

Massive MIMO schemes and architectures

Sub-THz D-MIMO assisted by a sub-6 GHz macro network

Fully digital architectures with low-resolution ADCs/DACs

KPIs: spectral efficiency, BER, cell capacity, throughput, coverage

KPIs: reduced complexity, reduced cost

Inclusiveness: Lowering cost for device

RIS-assisted transmission

Control procedures for externally controlled RIS in industrial environments

Signal analysis for RIS

RIS-assisted D-MIMO

Control procedures for personal RIS

Learn RIS-RM

KPIs: spectral efficiency, BER, cell capacity, throughput, coverage

KPIs: reduced energy consumption

Inclusiveness: increasing coverage, lowering cost, increased service availability
Sustainability: lowering EMF exposure

MIMO Transmission - D4.3

D4.3 - Early results of 6G Radio Key Enablers • 30/4/2024

Summary of D4.3

- Within the framework of 6G, MIMO is expected to have a significant role, offering the potential to enhance the capacity and efficiency of wireless communication systems even further to satisfy future communication demands. Chapter 5 focuses on exploring three techniques of MIMO within the context of 6G: **D-MIMO**, **massive MIMO**, and **RIS**.
- **D-MIMO**: It focuses on both coherent and non-coherent transmission, and explores decentralized transmission and analogue fronthaul, as well as investigates the rotary antenna and one-bit ADC system. Additionally, it discusses the sub-THz D-MIMO assisted by a sub-6GHz macro network.
- **Massive MIMO**: It includes the analysis of enhanced data detection using a 1-bit ADC, and explores the design of a beamformer for sub-THz frequencies, as well as the investigation of hybrid analogue-digital architectures for MIMO. Additionally, it discusses the multi-user MIMO and location-dependent coded caching.
- **RIS-assisted transmission**: It focuses on the discussion of D-MIMO-assisted with RIS and RIS-assisted IAB. In addition, this section investigates the channel estimation of RIS, RIS reflecting modulation (RIS-RM), and non-radiative RIS transmission.

MIMO Transmission

D-MIMO schemes and architectures

Non-coherent Space-time Coded Transmission

Problem Statement	The mmWave frequency band faces challenges in reliable communication due to high path loss and shadowing. Besides, channel estimation can be tricky in several scenarios, e.g., high mobility, lack of uplink/downlink reciprocity, hardware calibration conditions and pilot contamination. NC-JT schemes defined in 3GPP can be used to address these issues, however, it is not clear how to use them with distributed and massive number of antennas. The aim is to explore robust transmission modes in challenging conditions by using orthogonal space time frequency block codes (STFBC) in D-MIMO precoding to enhance diversity at the UE side and maintain certain data rates even without precise CSI.
Methodology	Proposed solutions: <ul style="list-style-type: none">• An RU-UE clustering is carried out to establish disjoint clusters of RUs jointly serving UEs, within each of which a suitable STFBC is going to be applied.• Alamouti-like orthogonal codes are used to realize the robust transmission mode, which use time, frequency and space diversity at the UE side.

- **Simulation settings:** Numerical simulations are performed in an indoor factory of area 120×60 meters, where operating frequency is 28 GHz with 200 MHz bandwidth.
- Path loss and shadowing is set as in 3GPP 38.901, and small-scale channel model is Rayleigh distributed. Maximum transmission power is 0.2W and UE noise figure is 9 dB.
- **Results:** the per-UE cumulative distribution functions (CDFs) for outage and ergodic SEs.
- STFBC together with optimized clustering outperforms baseline methods.
- A significant enhancement on 5th percentile user ergodic SEs can be achieved with STFBCs, while the mean values are similar both for STFBC and small-cell
- The clustering can optimize the worst-case SEs by maintaining a similar performance for all users on average.

Distributed OTA cooperative beamforming design

<p>Problem Statement</p>	<p>The DMIMO configuration diminishes intercell interference, making it especially well-suited for small-cell applications. In the literature on non-cooperative beamforming strategies, where each AP locally designs its beamformer without exchanging CSI through backhaul fronthaul links, recent studies highlight the potential for cooperative beamforming strategies to yield even greater performance gains. However, the cooperative beamforming design requires the CSI exchange via fronthaul links, which may not be feasible due to the fronthaul bandwidth limitations and not scalable. This work provides a cooperative beamforming design without exchanging the CSI via fronthaul links, using the bi-directional training.</p>
<p>Methodology</p>	<p>Proposed solutions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Considering the downlink communication, the cooperative beamformers is designed using bi-directional training, where the UEs update their combiners using downlink pilots (DL), and APs update their precoders using uplink pilots (UL-1 and UL-2) using iterative bi-directional training. The complexity of the proposed method is much less than the CPU based design.

• **Simulation settings:** Consider 25 BS placed on square grid of 500m×500m area. 16 multi-antenna UEs are randomly placed. The channel between UEs and APs follows Rayleigh fading, and the carrier frequency is 2.5 GHz.

• **Results:** The proposed method with OTA signalling, i.e., distributed-OTA, distributed GB, BR, BR-GS outperform the local MMSE, MF and centralized methods in both unicasting and multicasting.

• The number of OTA resources required for unicasting depends on the number of UEs, while the number of OTA resources required for multicasting depends on the number of multicasting groups.

• Note that the imperfect channel includes AWGN at APs and UEs.

D-MIMO with rotary ULAs

Problem Statement	Traditional wireless communication systems adopt static antennas, that is, antennas or antenna arrays without any movement capabilities. Movable antennas can exploit wireless channel variation in the continuous spatial domain. This additional degree of freedom can enhance the quality of wireless links, and consequently the communication performance. In this contribution, the performance of MU-MIMO systems where the APs are equipped with rotary ULA is studied. Considering an indoor industrial scenario, the numerical results show that the adoption of APs equipped with rotary ULAs can significantly enhance the mean per-user achievable SE when compared to deployments with static APs.
Methodology	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Single antenna devices are randomly and uniformly distributed on the coverage area. A random subset of K devices is active and seeks to transmit data in the uplink in each time slot. All devices are positioned at the same height.• Fully centralized processing is considered, where all the APs simultaneously serve all the devices, and they are connected to a common CPU through fronthaul connections. The CPU is responsible for performing all the signal processing tasks of the system.• Assume that there are no hardware impairments, and there is perfect synchronization among the APs. Moreover, CSI is available at the APs. CPU has estimated of the positions of all the devices subscribed to the network. The optimal position of the Q APs is jointly computed by the CPU.

- **Results:** The results for the APs equipped with static ULAs are compared to the results for the case of APs with the rotary ULAs. The curves the performance improvement of the rotary ULAs grows with the Rician factor.
- When the Rician factor is low, the wireless channels are dominated by NLoS components, and the rotation of the ULAs does not bring performance gains.
- When the Rician factor grows, the power of the LoS components increases. The rotation of the ULAs brings significant enhancement to the spectral efficiency.
- $Q=2$ and $Q=4$ achieve the best performance, which shows that there is a “sweet spot” between the number of APs and number of antenna elements per AP that yields the best performance.

Distributed-MIMO with analogue fronthaul

Problem Statement	D-MIMO introduces new challenges related to higher demands on bandwidth, synchronization, and power consumption. Therefore, innovative solutions are essential to harness the potential of D-MIMO in a cost-effective manner. Coherent joint transmission (CJT) involving two or more transmit/receive points (TRxPs) must be supported. However, meeting the stringent synchronization requirements with sub-nanosecond precision becomes crucial for CJT. One practical approach to achieving CJT is by employing analogue fronthaul (FH) links in combination with centralized processing since channel estimation includes the phase and amplitude change of both the wired path (i.e., FH) and wireless path of each transmitter, providing all the necessary information for CJT precoding.
Methodology	<ul style="list-style-type: none">A simple multiple-input single-output (MISO) setup is assumed involving an N-TRxP D-MIMO network and a single user equipment (UE). Both the UE and all TRxPs within the network are assumed to have a single antenna.

Results: 10 MHz OFDM signal carrying high-order 256-QAM symbols across all subcarriers. To assess D-MIMO flexibility with analogue FH links, TRxP 1 has an 800m fibre FH link, while TRxP 2 uses a 1.2m coaxial cable, resulting in a $\sim 3.897 \mu\text{s}$ delay difference.

- For fair CJT evaluation, the EVM performance for both TRxPs is nearly identical during separate transmissions. The measured delay difference of $3.906 \mu\text{s}$ closely aligns with the theoretical $3.897 \mu\text{s}$.
- For CJT, separate channel estimation is performed for TRxP 1 and TRxP 2. These estimates are used to compute the precoder for the TRxP 2 signal. The precoded signal is aligned in time in accordance with the measured delay difference between FH links.
- The CJT gain approximates ~ 5.35 dB when compared to TRxP 2 alone and approximately ~ 5.22 dB in comparison to TRxP 1.

MIMO Transmission

RIS-assisted transmission

D-MIMO assisted with RIS

Problem Statement	<p>In evolving 5G and future 6G networks, scalability of D-MIMO systems to large networks in a practically feasible way is challenging. Exploitation of cost-effective and energy-efficient dynamic clustering techniques, and densification enablers is crucial for such systems to sustain. RIS is well regarded as a low cost, rapidly deployable, energy-efficient candidate offering extra diversity in the spatial domain. This work explores RIS-aided multi-AP systems attaining certain prescribed KPIs, while considering the energy consumption in the system.</p>
Methodology	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To understand how RISs can help improve current communications systems, this study compares the performance of • A system consisting of 18 APs, each equipped with 16 antennas, communicating with 18 single-antenna UEs • The same system assisted by 18 RISs, each comprising 64 reflective elements • The system with RISs but with single-antenna APs • With $M_{RIS}=256$. • For easy of simulation, it is assumed assume that the RISs are always located with LoS to both the AP and the UE they assist.

- **Results:** The CDFs of the SINR experienced by the Ues and the feasible energy efficiency (EE) gains provided by RISs.
- For the case of 16-antenna APs: RISs can improve the median SINR from 18 dB to 21 dB. More importantly, the 10-percentile SINR is improved by about 6 dB.
- The right figure shows that even with P_b power dissipation values as high as 10 dBm per reflecting element, deploying RISs holds the potential for improving the system's energy efficiency.

RIS assisted integrated access and backhaul

<p>Problem Statement</p>	<p>The sub-urban IAB networks have been impacted by the tree foliage on signal propagation. The attenuation and scattering of wireless signals caused by leaves and branches can lead to a considerable performance degradation in these networks. Consequently, it is of utmost importance for network designers and operators to adopt innovative strategies, cope with such issues, especially in maintaining reliable and sufficient data rates in the backhaul links. RISs due to their unique capabilities, can be helpful in bypassing the tree foliage affected direct backhaul links. This work explores RIS-aided IAB system attaining certain prescribed KPIs, including service coverage probability.</p>
<p>Methodology</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The work is to optimize the network and address the tree foliage issue in IAB networks, for the sub-urban areas, focusing on the backhaul links. • A mmWave channel model is adapted, with 5G channel model (5GCM) urban macro (Uma) close in model for pathloss modelling. • Codebook-based beamforming is used due to its less complexity and better efficiency as it replaces the normal beamforming strategy with a comparatively simpler amplitude and phase-changing method.

- **Results:** The figure depicts the service coverage probability as a function of tree depth r for sub-urban use case considering in-leaf percentages, i.e., the percentages of leaf cover in the trees of 25% and 75% resembling the seasonal variations.
- For small r values, the traditional IAB network is depicting similar performance to a RIS-aided network.
- As the r becomes larger, the RIS-aided network outperforms the IAB only backhauled network.

Channel estimation for RIS

<p>Problem Statement</p>	<p>Considering a passive RIS, the uplink channel estimation schemes rely on the feedback received at the base station by transmitting a pilot sequence to estimate the channel. Further, a large number of reflecting elements are required at RIS to facilitate a satisfactory performance, which requires a large pilot overhead. Furthermore, the mobility of vehicles demands frequent channel estimation, thus creating an intolerable pilot overhead. This work focusses on uplink channel estimation under mobility in an RIS aided mm wave communication system. The objective of the study is to improve channel estimation accuracy while utilizing fewer pilot resources.</p>
<p>Methodology</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The study considers a pilot sequence corresponding to phase shifts at RIS obtained from a codebook. The received pilot symbols are used to estimate the channel parameters. • The resulting optimization problem is non-convex due to the coupling of optimization variables. Still, an approximate solution can be found using alternative optimization. • The accuracy of the solution is compromised due to power leakage caused by non-ideal angular grid. Therefore, a machine learning based approach is proposed to predict the AoAs.

- **Results:** The results compare the NMSE of the direct and RIS channels when using different channel estimation algorithms.
- The DeepMIMO dataset is used to generate channel parameters (i.e., AoAs, AoDs and complex path gains) for a system with carrier frequency 28 GHz.
- The figures show the NMSE performance of the proposed machine learning-based channel estimation algorithm (denoted as Algorithm 5 in the figure) in comparison to optimisation-based algorithm (denoted as Algorithm 4 in the figure) and the baseline with known AoAs, for stationary and mobile user scenarios.
- It can be observed that the machine learning solution outperform optimisation -based algorithm in both stationary and mobile user cases.

Control procedures for non-radiative RIS

Problem Statement	<p>There is a distinction between infrastructure RIS and personal RIS, where the latter is assumed to be located close to UEs, operate in mmWave or sub-THz spectrum and be transparent or non-transparent to the network. Given the considered target use cases of personal RIS and high frequency indoor propagation, the wireless control of RIS can be split between the UE, a local RIS controller and a remote controller of RIS whose placement is flexible. An investigation is carried out for the options of functionality split to identify the best one from the perspective of signalling overhead, latency and implementation complexity.</p>
Methodology	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The first option is based on the exchange of control model. In this case, remote controller periodically computes a control model and provides it to the local controller. The second option is based on the exchange of a pair of a codebook and a control model for UE. By codebook an enumerated set of RIS configurations is considered, where each configuration corresponds to a set of reflecting coefficients.

First option

- **Results:** The following advantages compared with baseline option without control split:
- Reduced communication overhead.
- Assistance for coverage extension.
- Privacy preserving.

Second option

Learn RIS reflecting modulation

Problem Statement	RIS-based communications with reflection modulation (RM) have garnered attention in literature as the RIS does not require additional RF chains to modulate information. The aim of this work is to provide a more scalable, less restricted solution that reduces BER for the more general application Jointly mapped RM, such that the RIS reflection patterns and transmit signals are jointly incorporated for the constellation design. In cases where the AP and user equipment (UE) direct link is NLoS, JRM can effectively deliver information to the user with the aid of the RIS and the joint constellation design.
Methodology	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• A single-user downlink system is studied under the full CSI assumption. The joint constellation is designed such that each constellation point comprises of a tuple of a transmit signal and a RIS reflection pattern.• The neighbouring RIS elements are grouped to have the same reflection coefficient to improve scalability and lower complexity in the design of the constellation and beamforming.• The RIS phase shifts are designed to align the phase of the effective channel, thus in jointly mapped quadrature RM, for a given reflection pattern, a group of elements are tuned to be orthogonal to the effective channel. In jointly mapped reflection pattern modulation (JRPM), a group of elements are turned off. An alternating optimization algorithm is used for the jointly active and passive beamforming design.

- **Results:** the BER performance of the proposed JQRM and JRPM schemes are compared with their respective theoretical upper bounds and equivalent SRM schemes, i.e., QRM and RPM, for SISO and MISO systems respectively.
- Both JQRM and JRPM shows superior BER performance compared to their separately mapped counterparts due to higher energy per bit achieved by the joint constellation design. The simulated BER of both JRPM and JQRM performs below their respective theoretical upper bounds. Overall, the QRM-based methods outperform the RPM-based methods due to the full aperture gain achieved by having all the RIS elements turned on.

Take home messages

Hexa-X-II D4.3 presents studies on various multiple-input, multiple-output (MIMO) techniques, MIMO, D-MIMO and RIS.

MIMO:

- The balance between spectral efficiency, sum rate, and energy efficiency has been deeply investigated in several contributions.
- The clustering approach is applied to enhance the performance of the worst user, while a proposed beamformer design primarily focuses on improving the average sum-rate performance.
- A collection of one-bit techniques have been proposed for finding a balance that maintains a satisfactory level of spectral efficiency while reducing energy consumption.

D-MIMO:

- The performance of the proposed rotary antenna is comparable to that of a conventional antenna.
- Massive MIMO (mMIMO) sub-THz is studied, showing that the sub-6GHz assisted and effective antenna dimension reduction can improve the performance of the sub-THz system.

RIS:

- RIS-assisted deployment techniques are considered, namely, integrated access and backhaul (IAB) and D-MIMO, as well as dynamic RIS channel estimation.
- Reflection modulation of RIS is also investigated in order to achieve low-rate data transmission.

- D4.2: “Radio Design and Spectrum Access requirements and key enablers for 6G Evolution”, Oct 2023.
- D4.3: “Early results of 6G Radio Key Enablers”, Apr. 2024.
- *D4.5: Final design of 6G Radio solutions and Promising Radio Innovations, Feb 2025.*

<https://hexa-x-ii.eu/results/>

HEXA-X-II.EU //

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